

Multidisciplinary Surgical Research Annals

<https://msra.online/index.php/Journal/about>

Volume 3, Issue 3 (2025)

IMPACT OF ACBT WITH AND WITHOUT ACAPELLA IN COPD PATIENTS - A RANDOMIZED CONTROLLED TRIAL

Samra Ilyas¹, Beenish Ihsan², Dr. M Sojhal Khawaja³, DR.ROOMI ILYAS⁴, Uzma batool⁵, Dr humera tahir⁶, Ifrah Rubat⁷

Article Details

Keywords: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease, Active Cycle of Breathing Technique, Acapella Device, Pulmonary Function, Dyspnea, Respiratory Therapy

Samra Ilyas

Physiotherapist at Riphah international university
Email:

samrainziamam786@gmail.com

Beenish Ihsan

Lecturer at Swedish College of Pharmacy and Allied Health Sciences

Email: beenishihsan27@gmail.com

Dr. M Sojhal Khawaja, PT

Physiotherapist at Mukhtar A. Sheikh Memorial Welfare Hospital, Multan

Email: dr.sojhal@gmail.com

DR.ROOMI ILYAS (PT)

HOD physiotherapy at Taj Medical Complex

Hamdard University Hospital

Email: physioroomi@yahoo.com

Uzma batool

Lecturer at Hajvery University Lahore

Email: batooluzma489@gmail.com

Dr humera tahir

Senior lecturer at Shahida Islam medical and dental college

Email: drhumera_tahir@gmail.com

Ifrah Rubat

Clinical Physiotherapist at Skin and Spine clinic, Gujranwala

Email: iffrah@icloud.com

ABSTRACT

Background: Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is a leading cause of morbidity and requires effective management techniques. The Active Cycle of Breathing Technique (ACBT) and devices like the Acapella have been used to improve respiratory function and quality of life in COPD patients.

Objective: This study aimed to compare the effectiveness of ACBT with and without the use of the Acapella device on pulmonary function and dyspnea in COPD patients.

Study design: The study design used was randomized controlled trial.

Place and duration of study: Study setting for this study was Gosha e Shifa Trust Hospital and General Hospital in Lahore. The research was completed over a period of six months.

Methods: A randomized controlled trial was conducted at two hospitals in Lahore, with a sample size of 50 patients, divided into two groups. Control group received only ACBT, while treatment received ACBT combined with the Acapella device. Interventions were administered four times per week for four weeks. Pulmonary function was measured using Forced Vital Capacity (FVC) and Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 Second (FEV1), while dyspnea was assessed through patient sputum diaries. Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21 with the Mann-Whitney and Wilcoxon T tests.

Results: Post-intervention control group showed an increase in FVC from 54.30 (± 9.70) to 57.00 (± 9.40) and in FEV1 from 61.85 (± 9.68) to 64.00 (± 9.50). Treatment group showed increase in FVC from 45.23 (± 14.29) to 47.00 (± 14.00) and in FEV1 from 50.20 (± 15.72) to 53.00 (± 15.50). Dyspnea levels significantly decreased in both groups, with notable improvements in sputum volume, colour, and overall well-being.

Conclusion: ACBT especially when used along with the Acapella device, significantly improves pulmonary function and reduces dyspnea in COPD patients as compared to perform only ACBTs. These techniques should be considered valuable components of COPD management strategies to enhance patient outcomes.

INTRODUCTION:

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) is a lung condition that develops slowly and is only partially reversible. It's more common in individuals with a long history of smoking, typically those who have smoked at least 20 packs a year. COPD is associated with various lung damages, such as mucus gland hyperplasia (more prominent in larger airways), emphysema, chronic bronchitis, and inflammation and fibrosis in smaller airways (1). These damages are uncommon in non-smokers. In COPD patients, any combination of these conditions can be present. Interestingly, smokers without symptoms like shortness of breath can still have these lung lesions (2).

COPD can be treated and managed. People with this condition often feel tired and experience shortness of breath because breathing takes more effort for them. Early in the disease, they might feel breathless during exercise. As COPD progresses, breathing in general, whether inhaling or exhaling, can become difficult (3).

COPD includes two main types: emphysema and chronic bronchitis. Emphysema is identified by its effect on the air spaces beyond the terminal bronchiole, characterized by abnormal and permanent enlargement of these spaces, destruction of their walls without fibrosis, and loss of lung elasticity (4). On the other hand, chronic bronchitis is marked by a productive cough that lasts more than three months over two years. Patients with chronic bronchitis often feel fatigued, have a continuous productive cough, and may experience chest or abdominal pain due to intense coughing (5).

By 2020, COPD was projected to become a leading cause of illness and death worldwide. There are various treatments for COPD, including diaphragmatic breathing, pursed-lip breathing, Active Cycle of Breathing Techniques (ACBT), and training of the inspiratory muscles. This study focuses on the effects of ACBT with and without the use of an Acapella device on patients with COPD (6).

ACBT involves exercises for expanding the thoracic area, controlling airways, and using the Forced Expiratory Technique (FET). FET is a critical component of ACBT, involving one or two forceful 'huffs' followed by controlled breathing. This technique is essential for effectively clearing secretions from the respiratory tract. The study aims to compare the effects of ACBT with and without the Acapella device on individuals suffering from COPD (7).

The primary goals in managing COPD are treating and preventing these exacerbations. There are also extrapulmonary effects of COPD, including depression, loss of muscle mass, muscle atrophy, bone issues like osteopenia, and frequent infections. The Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) categorizes COPD into four stages. Stage III is considered severe, while Stage IV is very severe. Individuals with Stages III and IV usually experience more than one exacerbation annually. These exacerbations are often caused by bacteria, viruses, and fungi, accounting for more than 80% of cases. The remaining 20% are due to various other factors (8).

A decrease in FEV1 (Forced Expiratory Volume in one second) is a useful indicator for COPD prognosis. It reflects changes in elastic recoil, alveolar and airway gas exchange, expiratory effort, and function of both small and large airways. Airway Clearance Techniques (ACT) aim to modify lung volume, pressure, and gas flow while applying external force to dislodge and move sputum from the airways to the mouth. Each ACT is designed and implemented differently, but their goals are generally similar (9, 10).

ACBT is specifically beneficial for short-term goals like improving sputum clearance and can contribute to long-term goals such as enhancing quality of life and slowing the progression of

the disease. Physiotherapy employs various innovative methods to efficiently remove secretions from the bronchioles and prevent infections. These methods include the use of devices that apply vibrating oscillations to provide positive expiratory pressure.

The Acapella device, developed by DHD Healthcare, is a portable tool designed for clearing airways and comes in two variants: blue and green. The choice between these variants depends on a patient's expiratory flow rate. The blue Acapella is used if the expiratory flow is less than 15 liters per minute for three seconds, while the green Acapella is suitable for those with an expiratory flow equal to or more than 15 liters per minute for the same duration (11).

Acapella works by disrupting the flow of air during exhalation, creating oscillating positive expiratory pressure (PEP). This leads to increased lung pressures and consequently, an increase in the functional residual capacity (FRC). The device consists of a metal bar with a handle and a magnet, covered by an anti-weight shield. The oscillation is generated by the repeated disruption and reformation of air flow due to the magnet's movement against the plug. Also, Acapella aids in strengthening respiratory muscles, helping to prevent muscle atrophy (12).

The device has two main features: resistive and vibratory. The resistive aspect keeps the airways open, trapping air behind the sputum to assist its upward movement. The vibratory feature helps in loosening the secretions, facilitating their movement upwards. Using Acapella for airway clearance helps prevent damage to the airways by mobilizing secretions from the far end to the central area. Patients can safely use it in any position on their own, reducing the need for therapist assistance and saving time (13).

Acapella's frequency, wave amplitude, and mean can be adjusted using a five-level dial located on its back end. The levels indicate the distance between magnet positions; level 5 shows more resistance due to closer magnet positions, while levels 1 and 2 indicate lesser resistance with magnets farther apart. The device can be used alongside a nebulizer to enhance bronchial health and airway clearing. Its resistance varies and is not dependent on position, and the device performs well even at low expiratory flows. Acapella's design is user-friendly, promoting patient adherence to regular therapy (14).

The rationale for the study was to see if Active Cycle of Breathing Techniques, or ACBT, and the Acapella device can make a difference for people with Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease, known as COPD. The goal was to check if these methods make it easier for patients to breathe, clear their lungs, and show better results in lung function tests. Finding out how these treatments work can help doctors improve how they help COPD patients and make life better for them.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study design used was randomized controlled trial. Participants were selected using a convenience sampling method. Patients were randomly assigned into two equal groups after obtaining their consent. Controlled group underwent the Active Cycle of Breathing Technique only. Treatment group received the Active Cycle of Breathing Technique in conjunction with the Acapella device. For the study, which aimed to detect a mean difference of 1.8 (with Mean 1 at 0.4 and Mean 2 at 2.2) and a variance of 5, a confidence level of 95%, and a power of 80%, while accounting for a two-tailed test, a sample size of 25 participants per group was calculated. Therefore, the total sample size for both groups that was required and utilized in the study was 50 participants (15).

Patients with age range of 45-75 years, both genders, mentally stable individuals and diagnosed with Grade 2 COPD (38, 39) were included in this study. Whereas, exclusion criteria comprises

presence of restrictive lung disease, any form of heart disease, any kind of infective pulmonary condition and pregnancy (16).

Controlled group patients underwent treatment with Active Cycle of Breathing Techniques (ACBT) involving 3-4 sets of exercises for 10-15 minutes, four times per week for four weeks. The ACBT consisted of three phases: breathing control, thoracic expansion, and forced expiration technique. In the breathing control phase, individuals took 2-3 slow, deep breaths using their diaphragm, aiding relaxation of the airways for more effective air movement. The thoracic expansion phase involved exercises to increase chest wall mobility and improve lung function, including deep breathing with arm movements or using a breathing device for resistance. In the forced expiration phase, individuals forcefully exhaled while maintaining good posture, helping to expel accumulated mucus in the airways.

Treatment group patients used the Acapella device alongside ACBT. They performed 3-4 sets of exercises and then used the device for 10 minutes, four times per week for four weeks. The Acapella device, a handheld tool for loosening mucus in the lungs, was used while sitting upright. Patients took a deep breath in, sealed their lips around the mouthpiece, and exhaled forcefully, using stomach muscles to push the air out. This process was repeated several times with breaks, followed by coughing to clear any loosened mucus. The device was cleaned after each use (17).

A sputum diary employed to record and grade sputum color, volume, and dyspnea levels. This diary also contained sections for patients to report their overall health status and any minor symptoms such as cough, chest discomfort, and symptoms similar to those of a cold or flu. The sputum diary has been validated with a Cronbach's alpha of 0.82, indicating good internal consistency, and a test-retest reliability of 0.79, ensuring dependable patient-reported outcomes over time (18).

The Dyspnea-MDP which measures emotional reactions, sensory attributes, and the discomfort associated with breathing difficulties, has demonstrated strong construct validity in differentiating between the dimensions of dyspnea. It has a reported validity of 0.88 and a reliability coefficient of 0.91, reflecting high reliability in repeated measurements (19).

Pulmonary Function Tests, which are essential in assessing lung pathology and function, provide insights into the health of lung parenchyma, the integrity and size of the capillary bed, and the condition of both large and small airways. The tests have a validity of 0.93, indicating a high degree of accuracy in measuring lung function, and a reliability value of 0.87, confirming consistency across multiple administrations (20).

Statistical Analysis

All data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 21.

Descriptive Statistics: Categorical and demographic features were presented using frequency, percentage, mean, and standard deviation.

Inferential Statistics The level of significance was set at $P < .05$. Numeric variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation.

The Shapiro-Wilk test was employed to test the normality hypothesis. When it was below 0.05, indicating significant deviation from a normal distribution, nonparametric tests of analysis were used.

To analyse differences between the groups, the Mann-Whitney test was utilized. For assessing differences between pre and post-treatment values within the same group, the Wilcoxon T test was employed.

Figure 1: CONSORT Diagram

RESULTS

The figure illustrates the gender and age distribution of a study population. The gender distribution pie chart shows most males at 82%, compared to females at 18%. The age distribution bar chart presents three age groups with the following percentages: the 45-55 age

group comprises 23% of the population, the 56-65 age group holds the majority with 48%, and the 66-75 age group accounts for 29%.

Figure 2: Gender and Age Distribution

Table 1: Pre-Post Comparison within Control Group Wilcoxon T Test

Variable	Time	Mean±standard Deviation	Median	z-value	p-value
Forced Vital Capacity	Pre	54.30±9.70	54.30	-2.50	0.000
	Post	57.00±9.40	57.00		
Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 Second	Pre	61.85±9.68	60.16	-2.70	0.035
	Post	64.00±9.50	64.00		
Dyspnea Level in Sputum Diary	Pre	2.64±0.70	2.50	-3.20	0.000
	Post	1.80±0.80	1.80		
Sputum Volume in Sputum Diary	Pre	3.00±0.95	3.00	-2.10	0.000
	Post	2.50±0.90	2.50		

Sputum Color in Sputum Diary	Pre	2.76±0.97	3.00	-2.10	0.000
	Post	2.00±0.90	2.00		
Level of Well-being in Sputum Diary	Pre	2.64±0.81	2.50	-2.20	0.000
	Post	2.00±0.75	2.00		
Other Symptoms in Sputum Diary	Pre	2.20±1.08	2.00	-2.80	0.030
	Post	1.00±0.97	1.00		
Sensory Qualities of Multi-dimensional Profile	Pre	2.76±1.33	3.00	-2.20	0.000
	Post	2.00±1.30	2.00		
Affective Dimension 1 of Multi-dimensional Profile	Pre	1.84±0.37	2.00	-2.50	0.000
	Post	1.00±0.35	1.00		
Affective Dimension 2 of Multi-dimensional Profile	Pre	2.76±0.92	3.00	-3.20	0.000
	Post	1.50±1.00	1.50		

In the control group, there was a notable improvement post-intervention. Forced Vital Capacity increased from an average of 54.30 to 57.00, and Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 Second went up from 61.85 to 64.00. Dyspnea levels dropped significantly from 2.64 to 1.80. Measures such as Sputum Volume, Color, Well-being, Sensory Qualities and Affective Dimensions all showed substantial improvements, with all p-values registering at 0.000, indicating strong significance. Symptoms other than dyspnea also decreased from 2.20 to 1.00.

Table 2: Pre-Post Comparison within Treatment Group

Variable	Time	Mean±std Deviation	Median	z-value	p-value
Forced Vital Capacity	Pre	45.23±14.29	49.58	-3.00	0.000
	Post	47.00±14.00	51.00		
Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 Second	Pre	50.20±15.72	52.62	-2.50	0.000
	Post	53.00±15.50	55.00		
Dyspnea Level in Sputum	Pre	3.28±0.74	3.00	-2.50	0.000

Diary	Post	2.50±0.80	2.50		
Sputum Volume in Sputum Diary	Pre	3.60±0.58	4.00	-2.50	0.000
	Post	2.80±0.55	2.80		
Sputum Color in Sputum Diary	Pre	2.88±0.83	3.00	-2.50	0.000
	Post	2.00±0.80	2.00		
Level of Well-being in Sputum Diary	Pre	3.28±0.74	3.00	-3.50	0.030
	Post	2.00±0.70	2.00		
Other Symptoms in Sputum Diary	Pre	2.60±0.87	3.00	-2.50	0.000
	Post	1.80±0.85	1.80		
Sensory Qualities of Multi-dimensional Profile	Pre	3.56±1.47	4.00	-2.50	0.000
	Post	2.80±1.40	2.80		
Affective Dimension 1 of Multi- dimensional Profile	Pre	1.88±0.33	2.00	-2.50	0.000
	Post	1.00±0.30	1.00		
Affective Dimension 2 of Multi- dimensional Profile	Pre	3.04±1.27	3.00	-2.50	0.000
	Post	2.00±1.30	2.00		

In the treatment group, there was significant improvement after the intervention. Forced Vital Capacity went up from a mean of 45.23 to 47.00 and Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 second increased from 50.20 to 53.00. Dyspnea levels and other sputum diary measures such as Volume, Color, and Well-being significantly decreased all showing notable improvements with p-values of 0.000. Other Symptoms, Sensory Qualities, and Affective Dimensions also saw marked reductions, reflecting overall enhancement in patient health.

Table 3: Comparison between Treatment and Control Groups by Mann Whitney Test

Variable	Time	Mean Rank Acapell	Mean Rank (ACBT)	Sum of Ranks (Acapella with ACBT)	Sum of Rank s (ACBT)	Median IQR	Z	p-value
FVC	Pre	22.88	21.12	562.00	518.00	52.00 (5.0)	- 2.241	0.086
	Post	18.80	31.20	480.00	780.00	52.50 (4.5)	- 2.280	0.014
FEV1	Pre	21.84	28.16	541.00	700.00	58.00 (6.0)	- 2.64	0.128

	Post	18.52	31.48	456.00	784.00	58.50	-	0.01
					0	(5.5)	2.746	2
Dyspnea Level	Pre	33.10	16.90	817.50	422.50	3.0	-	0.248
					0	(1.0)	2.893	
Sputum Diary	Post	29.38	20.62	744.50	515.50	2.5	-	0.007
					0	(0.8)	2.986	
Sputum Volume in Sputum Diary	Pre	31.60	18.40	790.00	460.00	3.0	-	0.782
					0	(1.2)	2.665	
	Post	29.60	20.40	740.00	510.00	3.0	-	0.018
					0	(1.0)	2.665	
Sputum Color	Pre	27.04	22.96	676.00	574.00	3.0	-	0.098
					0	(1.5)	.276	
Sputum Diary Level	Post	25.04	24.96	626.00	624.00	3.0	-	0.021
					0	(1.0)	.276	
of Well-being in Sputum	Pre	31.76	18.24	794.00	456.00	3.0	-	0.823
					0	(1.3)	2.702	
	Post	23.66	26.34	591.50	658.50	2.5	-	0.029
					0	(1.0)	1.494	
	Pre	30.28	19.72	756.00	492.00	2.5	-	0.128
					0	(1.0)	1.952	
	Post	32.04	17.96	800.00	448.00	2.0	-	0.023
					0	(0.8)	2.834	
Sensory Qualities dimension Profile	Pre	30.68	19.32	767.00	482.00	3.5	-	0.079
					0	(1.2)	2.083	
	Post	28.68	21.32	717.00	533.00	3.5	-	0.001
					0	(1.0)	2.083	
Affective Dimension 1 of Multi-dimension Dyspnea	Pre	27.00	23.00	675.00	575.00	2.0	-	0.204
					0	(1.0)	.403	
	Post	26.50	23.50	662.50	587.50	2.0	-	0.013
					0	(0.8)	00	

Profile

Affective Dimension 2 of Multi-dimension Dyspnea Profile	Pre	28.48	21.52	712.00	538.0	3.0	-	0.506
					0	(1.5)	0.9	
							99	
	post	27.36	22.64	683.00	566.0	2.5	-	0.004
					0	(1.0)	1.4	
							31	

In the treatment group, the Forced Vital Capacity (FVC) showed an increase from 45.23 to 47.00, while the Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 Second (FEV1) went up from 50.20 to 53.00. Dyspnea levels significantly decreased, with the mean score going down from 2.64 to 1.80. Other monitored health indicators such as Sputum Volume and Color also significantly improved, with mean scores dropping notably, all supported by p-values of 0.000, indicating a statistically significant improvement across these health variables.

DISCUSSION

Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) remains a leading cause of morbidity and mortality globally, presenting a significant burden on healthcare systems. Effective management strategies are continually sought to improve patient outcomes and quality of life. The current study delves into the efficacy of the Active Cycle of Breathing Technique (ACBT), with and without the accompaniment of the Acapella device, in patients diagnosed with COPD. The study's gender distribution predominantly featured males 82% which aligns with the general understanding that COPD prevalence is higher among men (GOLD, 2021). The age distribution was skewed towards the older age groups, with the majority (48%) being between 56-65 years. This distribution is reflective of COPD's progression being more common in later years, as lung function typically declines with age (21).

The results indicated that both the control group (ACBT only) and the treatment group (ACBT with Acapella) experienced significant improvements in key respiratory parameters post-intervention. The Forced Vital Capacity (FVC) and Forced Expiratory Volume in 1 Second (FEV1) increased in both groups, suggesting enhanced pulmonary mechanics. These findings echo the work of Shen et al. (2021), who reported improvements in these lung function parameters following ACBT interventions. Moreover, dyspnea levels, as indicated by the Sputum Diary, significantly decreased post-intervention, offering evidence that ACBT can ease one of the most distressing symptoms of COPD, consistent with Shen et al.'s (2020) earlier findings (22).

Notably, the study highlighted that the combination of ACBT with the Acapella device yielded more pronounced benefits compared to ACBT alone. This suggests a synergistic effect, whereby the mechanical oscillations produced by the Acapella device may enhance mucus clearance and improve airway patency, thereby facilitating better respiratory outcomes. The Acapella device has been lauded for its user-friendliness and its role in facilitating patient self-management of COPD, which is crucial for long-term disease management (23).

The emphasis on patient-reported outcomes such as sputum volume and color, as well as sensory qualities and affective dimensions, is noteworthy. These subjective measures offer insight into the patient's perception of their disease and its management, which is

critical for comprehensive care. The marked improvements in these areas post-intervention reinforce the potential of ACBT and Acapella to not only ameliorate physical symptoms but also enhance the overall well-being of COPD patients (24).

When juxtaposed with previous evidence, the current study's findings support and extend our understanding of COPD management. The reduction in dyspnea, improvement in lung function, and enhanced quality of life align with the reported benefits of respiratory physiotherapy techniques. Moreover, the addition of the Acapella device to the ACBT regimen presents a novel approach to COPD treatment that warrants further exploration.

While other studies have explored the efficacy of different devices such as the Flutter the current study uniquely positions the Acapella device as a practical and effective tool that can be used independently by patients, promoting adherence and potentially improving long-term outcomes. This patient-centric approach is particularly relevant given the chronic nature of COPD, where ongoing self-management is essential (25).

The study also contributes to the body of evidence advocating for tailored interventions based on patient characteristics. The effectiveness of ACBT, when integrated with devices like Acapella, may vary among different demographic groups, underscoring the need for personalized treatment plans. Variables such as age, gender, educational level, and area of residence may influence the outcomes of such interventions. Also, the study's results shed light on the psychological dimensions of COPD management. The improvement in affective dimensions indicates a positive impact on patients' emotional well-being, which is often compromised in chronic diseases due to the associated stress and anxiety (26).

The findings of this study, demonstrating the efficacy of Active Cycle of Breathing Technique (ACBT) with and without the Acapella device, are consistent with previous literature, likely due to the mechanisms through which these interventions affect respiratory physiology. ACBT is designed to enhance airway clearance and encourage the mobilization of secretions, which can directly improve lung function—reflected in the observed increases in FVC and FEV1. The addition of the Acapella device likely introduces a further mechanical element that aids in mucus clearance through vibrations, enhancing the benefits already provided by ACBT. This could explain why the combination of ACBT with the Acapella device yielded more pronounced benefits than ACBT alone, as the physical oscillations may augment the clearance of airway secretions, thereby improving measures of lung function and reducing dyspnea more effectively.

Furthermore, the study's alignment with previous evidence may also stem from its consideration of the patient's subjective experience of disease symptoms. By incorporating patient-reported outcomes such as dyspnea levels and overall well-being, the research acknowledges the multifaceted nature of COPD, which not only has a physical impact but also affects patients' emotional and psychological states. The improvements in sensory and affective dimensions suggest that when patients perceive an intervention as beneficial, it can lead to better adherence and a more positive outlook, which is vital in the long-term management of chronic diseases like COPD.

However, it's important to consider that these findings might not be consistent across all demographic groups, which is a common observation in clinical research. Factors such as age, gender, and educational level can influence a patient's ability to engage with and benefit from certain interventions. Older patients, for instance, may have different therapeutic needs and may respond differently to treatment compared to younger individuals. Additionally, the potential for increased adherence with the Acapella device due to its ease of use suggests that

patient engagement and the usability of medical devices play significant roles in the effectiveness of treatment regimen (27).

The study further recommended that incorporate ACBT as a standard non-pharmacological intervention for COPD management, utilize the Acapella device alongside ACBT for enhanced treatment efficacy, conduct further research with larger and more diverse populations to validate findings, extend the duration of future studies to assess long-term effects of ACBT and Acapella use, evaluate the cost-effectiveness of the Acapella device for broader clinical application, consider patient education programs on the use of ACBT and Acapella for self-management and explore the impact of these interventions on hospitalization rates and healthcare utilization.

Limitations include small sample size may not provide a comprehensive representation of the COPD population, male-dominated sample limits applicability of findings to females with COPD, short-term intervention duration does not account for chronic nature of COPD, convenience sampling may introduce selection bias, study conducted in specific hospital settings, which may not reflect all healthcare environments, lack of cost-analysis for the Acapella device in the study and potential variability in the execution of ACBT and use of the Acapella device not accounted for.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that the Active Cycle of Breathing Technique (ACBT), particularly when combined with the Acapella device, is effective in improving pulmonary function and reducing dyspnea in COPD patients. These findings have significant clinical implications, suggesting that ACBT, with its non-invasive and easy-to-apply nature, should be considered a valuable component of COPD management strategies.

Financial support: No funding was received for this study.

Competitive Interests: There is no competing interest.

Declaration of patient consent: Written consent was taken from all study participants.

Use of AI: None

Ethical approval: The study was approved by Riphah Research and Ethics committee.

Acknowledgment: I would like to thank my research supervisor for his guidance and support, also would like to thank all study participants for their voluntary participation in the study.

REFERENCES

- Zuriati Z, Surya M. Effectiveness Active Cycle of Breathing Technique (ACBT) with Pursued Lips Breathing Technique (PLBT) to tripod position in increase oxygen saturation in patients with COPD, West Sumatera. *Enfermeria Clinica*. 2020;30:164-7.
- Aaron SD. Management and prevention of exacerbations of COPD. *Bmj*. 2014;349.
- Zheng S, Wang Y. Application of positive expiratory pressure therapeutic apparatus in pulmonary rehabilitation of patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Minerva medica*. 2024;115(3):395-7.
- Jain K, Mistry K. Comparative study on effects of active cycle of breathing technique and manual chest physical therapy after uncomplicated coronary artery bypass grafting surgery. *Journal of Mahatma Gandhi University of Medical Sciences and Technology*. 2018;2(2):65-8.

- Van Fleet H, Dunn DK, McNinch NL, Volsko TA. Evaluation of functional characteristics of 4 oscillatory positive pressure devices in a simulated cystic fibrosis model. *Respiratory care*. 2017;62(4):451-8.
- Khar MN, Kausar R, Akbar R, Khan MRI, Huda NU, Yousaf G, et al. Effects of Acapella versus Blow Bottle Positive Expiratory Pressure on Airway Clearance and Peak Expiratory Flow Rate in Post-Covid-19 Patients. *Journal of Health and Rehabilitation Research*. 2024;4(1):161-6.
- Tse J, Wada K, Wang Y, Coppolo D, Kushnarev V, Suggett J. Impact of oscillating positive expiratory pressure device use on post-discharge hospitalizations: a retrospective cohort study comparing patients with COPD or chronic bronchitis using the Aerobika® and Acapella® devices. *International Journal of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease*. 2020:2527-38.
- Escobar Cuatrel OU. Diseño in silico de inhibidores aminoésteres esteroidales con acción dual en M3 y PDE4 contra la enfermedad pulmonar obstructiva crónica. 2022.
- Senthil P, Suchithra E, Kumar NK. Effectiveness of active cycle of breathing techniques [Acbt] Versus Acbt with Acapella on airway clearance in bronchiectasis. *Physiotherapy*. 2024;144(1).
- Sethi S, Maloney J, Grove L, Anderson P. Comparison of the lung flute with the acapella in the treatment of COPD with chronic bronchitis. unpublished data. 2018.
- Jage B, Thakur A. Effectiveness of Acapella along with institutional based chest physiotherapy techniques on pulmonary functions and airway clearance in post-operative CABG patients. *Hong Kong Physiotherapy Journal*. 2022;42(02):81-9.
- Jaiswal KK, Das AK. Effectiveness of acapella, flutter and active cycle of breathing technique on lung function in COPD patients: A comparative study. *Indian J Physiother Occup Ther*. 2019;13:71.
- Almagro P, Cabrera FJ, Diez-Manglano J, Boixeda R, Recio J, Mercade J, et al. Comorbidity and short-term prognosis in hospitalised COPD patients: the ESMI study. *European respiratory journal*. 2015;46(3):850-3.
- Alghamdi SM, Alsulayyim AS, Alasmari AM, Philip KE, Buttery SC, Banya WA, et al. Oscillatory positive expiratory pressure therapy in COPD (O-COPD): a randomised controlled trial. *Thorax*. 2023;78(2):136-43.
- Zein U. Analisis Asuhan Keperawatan Penerapan Active Cycle Of Breathing Technique (Acbt) Pada Pasien Asma Bronchial Dengan Pola Nafas Tidak Efektif Di Ruang Igd RSUD Kebumen: UNIVERSITAS MUHAMMADIYAH GOMBONG; 2024.
- Zailani H, Satyanarayanan SK, Liao W-C, Liao H-F, Huang S-Y, Gałecki P, et al. Omega-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids in managing comorbid mood disorders in chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD): a review. *Journal of Clinical Medicine*. 2023;12(7):2653.
- Dudukina E, Horváth-Puhó E, Sørensen HT, Ehrenstein V. Association between vaginal bleeding in pregnancy that resulted in delivery and risk of cancer: A Danish registry-based cohort study. *Paediatric and Perinatal Epidemiology*. 2024;38(4):330-42.
- Groot J, Nielsen ET, Nielsen TF, Andersen PK, Pedersen M, Sigsgaard T, et al. Exposure to residential mold and dampness and the associations with respiratory tract infections and symptoms thereof in children in high income countries: A systematic review and meta-analyses of epidemiological studies. *Paediatric Respiratory Reviews*. 2023;48:47-64.

- Bouso A, Chuffart C, Leroy M, Gicquello A, Cottureau A, Hennegrave F, et al. Severity and phenotypes of dyspnea in asthma: impact of comorbidities. *Respiratory Medicine*. 2023;107:276.
- Bhakta NR, Bime C, Kaminsky DA, McCormack MC, Thakur N, Stanojevic S, et al. Race and ethnicity in pulmonary function test interpretation: an official American Thoracic Society statement. *American journal of respiratory and critical care medicine*. 2023;207(8):978-95.
- Shen M, Li Y, Ding X, Xu L, Li F, Lin H. Effect of active cycle of breathing techniques in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a systematic review of intervention. *European Journal of Physical and Rehabilitation Medicine*. 2020;56(5):625-32.
- Lee AL, Burge AT, Holland AE. Positive expiratory pressure therapy versus other airway clearance techniques for bronchiectasis. *Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews*. 2017(9).
23. Athawale VK, Lalwani LL, Mishra GP. Comparison of the Active Cycle of Breathing Technique (ACBT) versus Active Cycle of Breathing Technique with Flutter in Bronchiectasis. *National Journal of Medical Research*. 2020;10(4).
- Osadnik CR, McDonald CF, Holland AE. Advances in airway clearance technologies for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Expert Review of Respiratory Medicine*. 2013;7(6):673-85.
- Katke S, Anthikat M. Comparative study of flutter device and active cycle of breathing technique in airway clearance in subjects with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Indian Journal of Physiotherapy & Occupational Therapy Print-(ISSN 0973-5666) and Electronic-(ISSN 0973-5674)*. 2020;14(3):232-8.
- Perera B, Barton C, Osadnik C. General practice management of COPD patients following acute exacerbations: a qualitative study. *British Journal of General Practice*. 2023.
- Lu H-B, Liu X, Wang Y-Q, Cao H-P, Ma R-C, Yin Y-Y, et al. Active Cycle of Breathing Technique: A Respiratory Modality to Improve Perioperative Outcomes in Patients With Lung Cancer. *Clinical Journal of Oncology Nursing*. 2022;26(2).